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Amperometric Estimation of Copper with Benzimidazole-2-Carboxylic Acid

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BENZIMIDAZOLE-2-carboxylic acid has been utilized as a reagent for amperometric estimation of copper. A manual polarographic set complete with potentiometer and a suitable spot-reflecting galvanometer as the current-measuring device was used for the titrations and for recording polarograms. A buffer solution containing 0.1M sodium acetate and 0.1M acetic acid (pH 4.6) has been found to be the most appropriate medium for conducting the titrations, in which copper is quantitatively precipitated by this reagent. The use of a little gelatine (0.01%) in the titrating solution serves as a maximum-suppressor. The titrations are best carried out at a potential of -0.5 volt (vs. S.C.E.) using dropping mercury electrode at which the diffusion current due to the reaction $\text{Cu(II)} \rightarrow \text{Cu(O)}$ is fully developed, whereas the reagent suffers very little change.

Benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid was prepared and purified by the method described in literature¹. The reagent solutions (0.1M and 0.025M) were prepared in 1:1 aqueous ethanol containing calculated amount of KOH to effect the solution of the reagent. The strength of the copper solution was verified iodometrically. For the purpose of amperometric titrations, a number of copper solutions containing varying copper concentrations were prepared from definite aliquot portions of the standard copper solution, the buffer solution and the gelatine solution. Titrations were conducted at room temperature (~30°). The end-point was accurately determined by the graphical method from the point of intersection of two arms of an L-shaped curve (Fig. 1), obtained by plotting the galvanometer deflections (current values) against the volume of the reagent solution added, applying the usual volume corrections to account for the dilution effect of the titrating solution. Copper solutions containing 6 mg. to 2 mg. copper were titrated with 0.1M reagent solution, whereas those from 1 mg. to 0.5 mg. with 0.025M reagent solution. Some typical results are shown in the Table 1. Copper can be estimated by this method in presence of appreciable amounts of

metallic ions like Zn^{++} , Mn^{++} , Co^{++} , Ni^{++} , Cd^{++} , Pb^{++} , Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} without any

Fig. 1

A typical curve of amperometric titration of copper(II) solution with benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid.

V = initial volume of Cu(II) solution titrated.

v = volume of titre solution added.

The upward arrow indicates the equivalent of actual copper content.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF COPPER WITH BENZIMIDAZOLE-2-CARBOXYLIC ACID

Total volume titrated = 15 ml.

Present (mg)	Copper	
	Found (mg)	Error (%)
6.00	6.01	+0.17
4.00	4.00	0.00
2.00	2.00	0.00
1.00	1.00	0.00
0.50	0.498	-0.40

interference. Copper was estimated in presence of Fe^{+++} by adding sufficient amount of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{HF}_2$ before titration. For titration in presence of Pb^{++} and Ni^{++} , a different buffer solution containing 0.05M sodium acetate and 0.95M acetic acid (pH 3.4) was used.

The above titration procedure was applied with satisfactory results in the estimation of copper in a sample of standard leaded brass having the composition: Cu, 59.82%; Zn, 34.95%; Fe, 0.82%; Pb, 3.54%; Sn, 0.80%.

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